

Chemical Vapor Infiltrated SiC

Matrix Composites

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The characteristics of ceramic matrix composites fabricated by gas phase infiltration will be discussed. SiC matrix composites reinforced with Nicalon (Nippon Carbon Co.) and Nextel (3M Co.) fibers have been fabricated by chemical vapor infiltration. It will be shown that tough, fracture resistant composites have resulted and that the CVD process is capable of producing a wide variety of shapes and sizes of articles.

